

Conference Abstract

A Centralized Web Platform for eLTER Romania: Connecting Observations, Research, and Decision-Making

Mihai Adamescu[‡], Alexandru Dumitrescu[§], Vasile Craciunescu[§], Tudor Racoviceanu[‡], Constantin Cazacu[‡], Magdalena Bucur[‡]

[‡] University of Bucharest, Research Center in Systems Ecology and Sustainability, Bucharest, Romania
[§] National Meteorological Administration, Bucharest, Romania

Corresponding author: Mihai Adamescu (mihaicristian.adamescu@g.unibuc.ro)

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Abstract

The **eLTER Romania Web Platform** is designed to support long-term ecosystem research by integrating **in situ observations, remote sensing data, and advanced analytics**. This platform serves as a **centralized data hub** for environmental monitoring across Romania developed under the eLTER network part of the European infrastructure, enabling researchers, policymakers, and stakeholders to access, visualize, and analyze ecological data efficiently.

The platform features **automated data ingestion**, integrating real-time observations from **environmental monitoring stations**, remote sensing products from **Copernicus (Sentinel-2, Sentinel-3, Sentinel-5P)**, and climate models. A **GIS-based decision-support system** enhances spatial analysis, allowing users to assess ecosystem dynamics, biodiversity trends, and environmental changes over time.

Key functionalities include:

a) **Stakeholder & Research Dashboard** – Providing interactive maps, time-series analysis, and ecosystem indicators;

- b) **Data Integration & Interoperability** – Connecting field stations, remote sensing datasets, and global observatories;
- c) **AI-Powered Analytics** – Identifying patterns in ecosystem health, biodiversity shifts, and climate impacts (to be done in the future);
- d) **Citizen Science & Public Engagement Tools** – Facilitating participatory data collection and ecosystem monitoring;
- e) **Learning & Collaboration Hub** – Offering training modules, research publications, and case studies.

The platform is designed to **support FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles**, ensuring seamless integration with European research infrastructures such as **LifeWatch and ICOS**. By providing standardized data interfaces and enabling real-time environmental monitoring, it enhances **long-term ecosystem research and adaptive management strategies**.

This initiative aligns with **EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030** and the goals of the **eLTER ESFRI** research infrastructure, fostering **scientific collaboration, open data access, and evidence-based policy decisions**. The **eLTER Romania Web Platform** will serve as a **dynamic, scalable, and interactive system**, driving innovation in environmental research and ecological sustainability.

Presenting author

Mihai Adamescu

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.